

Exploring ORCID adoption and metadata presence in Spain's research landscape

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Abstract

In the evolving landscape of scientific research, ORCID identifiers are essential for maintaining academic integrity and enhancing research visibility. This study proposes a methodological framework for identifying and analyzing the presence and characteristics of researchers in a specific country in ORCID, using complementary data from OpenAlex to improve results. Our objectives were to develop a reliable method to identify ORCID records of researchers in Spain, study the frequency of profile updates, and investigate the most frequently filled metadata sections and common profile characteristics across disciplines. We identified 190,455 ORCID records of Spanish researchers and found high engagement with some metadata, particularly in the 'Employment' (73%) and 'Publications' (83%) sections. Additionally, 73% of records were actively maintained. The most common metadata combination included 'Works', 'Employment', and 'Education and Qualifications'. However, we noted significant variability and incomplete records across disciplines. The study highlights the need for more complete and frequently updated profiles, improved institutional integration, and strategic efforts to enhance ORCID adoption. These improvements could enhance the reliability of ORCID for tracking researcher mobility and academic trajectories.

Keywords: ORCID; OpenAlex; scientometrics; Spain; researcher profiles

Key points

- A methodological framework has been proposed for accurately identifying researchers from a specific country within the ORCID database.
- 73% of the 190,455 ORCID records of Spanish researchers are active.
- Key fields like 'Employment' and 'Works' are highly populated, while 'Keywords' and 'Peer review' are less frequently filled.
- Common metadata combinations often include 'Works', 'Employment', 'Education and Qualifications', and 'Other IDs'.
- The majority of ORCID records fall under Physical Sciences followed by Social Sciences, Health Sciences, and Life Sciences.

48 **1. INTRODUCTION**

49 In the current dynamic and global context of ever-changing scientific research, persistent
50 identifiers (PIDs) have become an important tool for researchers, facilitating reliable
51 discovery, citation, and interlinking of digital resources over time. PIDs address the
52 complexities introduced by shifting locations and access methods to information
53 (Meadows et al., 2019). Adopting these identifiers helps track scholarly patterns and keep
54 academic integrity and enhances knowledge networks, proving essential for the scholarly
55 system (Macgregor et al., 2023). By enabling seamless interconnection, interoperability
56 of information, and cross-disciplinary collaborations, PIDs are crucial for maintaining the
57 coherence and continuity of the open science ecosystem, thereby bolstering its core
58 principles of transparency, accessibility, and scientific collaboration (Anglada & Abadal,
59 2018).

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61 The shift towards an open science paradigm needs research infrastructures that provide
62 open scholarly metadata, enhancing the visibility, openness, aggregation, and
63 management of research outputs (Bornmann et al., 2021; Peroni & Shotton, 2020). In this
64 context, ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier) has become pivotal.
65 ORCID stands out by offering a unique and persistent identification system that bridges
66 authors with their diverse contributions across the academic and research landscapes. It
67 achieves this through ORCID IDs, which not only link researchers to their works,
68 activities, and affiliations but also help these contributions be accurately recognized and
69 transparently managed in the scholarly ecosystem (ORCID, 2024a).

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71 The integration of ORCID thus represents a significant advance in the organization of the
72 academic landscape, promoting transparency in the registration and acknowledged of
73 researchers' efforts. Nevertheless, it has been posited that the motivation of researchers
74 to engage with ORCID is primarily driven by mandates from publishing and funding
75 entities within the research ecosystem (Porter, 2022; Teixeira da Silva, 2021b) rather than
76 the intrinsic advantages associated with maintaining an ORCID profile. This perspective
77 emphasises a compliance-driven adoption and highlight the need to effectively
78 communicate and leverage the intrinsic value of ORCID profiles to researchers
79 themselves. This may be attributed to the complexity of integrating ORCID into existing
80 research infrastructures (Dappert et al., 2017; Schnieders et al., 2022).

81
82 Although the adoption of ORCID as a PID for unique author identification is becoming
83 increasingly common (Haak et al., 2012), there are several challenges that researchers
84 face when working with ORCID as a data source for scientometric studies. For example,
85 there is a significant lack of adoption and completeness in ORCID records that varies
86 across disciplines (Fernández-Marcial et al., 2023), the hard sciences tend to lead in
87 adoption and completeness, in contrast to the social sciences, arts, and humanities
88 (Boudry & Durand-Barthez, 2020; Bordons et al., 2024), and also across countries which
89 leads to biases in coverage (Youtie et al., 2017). Previous studies have identified quality
90 data issues such as empty records, problems with homonyms, sections with outdated data,
91 multiple profiles for the same author (Heusse & Cabanac, 2022; Wang et al., 2024); the

92 occurrence of duplicate and fake profiles (Baglioni, Mannocci, et al., 2021; Teixeira da
93 Silva, 2021a; 2021c), the creation of profiles by personnel not directly linked to research
94 (Heusse & Cabanac, 2022), regular update of profiles (Costas et al., 2022),
95 misidentification of authors and their associated institutions (Martínez-Méndez & Lopez-
96 Carreño, 2019), the creation of “silent” or 'ghost' profiles (Teixeira da Silva, 2021a; 2023;
97 Wang et al., 2024) and the limitations in data verification (Wang et al., 2024).
98 Furthermore, there is a lack of standardization of information, which often reflects a
99 compliance response to mandates from both publishers and funders (Choraś &
100 Jaroszevska-Choraś, 2020; Porter, 2022; Teixeira da Silva, 2022).

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102 Despite these challenges, researchers generally have a positive perception of PIDs and
103 their scientific infrastructure. However, there is a pressing need for user training to avoid
104 inconsistencies and errors (Houghton & Foster, 2024), and dissemination efforts are
105 crucial to address the evident unawareness about their identification, purpose, and utility.
106 This lack of knowledge varies across disciplines and scholarly occupations (Macgregor
107 et al., 2023). In this line, the importance of developing and implementing projects by
108 research institutions, along with promotional campaigns, has been identified as crucial
109 tools for successful ORCID adoption and use within the research community
110 (Aghassibake et al., 2023; Pampel et al., 2024).

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112 To date, there has been a lack of prior systematic studies investigating these phenomena
113 in Spain. This paper aims to fill this gap in the literature by comprehensively analysing
114 the adoption and use of ORCID identifiers and metadata completeness for Spanish
115 researchers. To address this research, the following specific objectives have been
116 established:

- 117 1. To develop a methodology for accurately identifying Spanish researchers
118 within the ORCID database, providing a reliable base for further analysis of
119 the adoption rate and data completeness.
- 120 2. To investigate the metadata sections most frequently updated and completed
121 by Spanish researchers in their ORCID profiles.
- 122 3. To explore the differences across disciplines to observe if there are any
123 discernible patterns in this regard.

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125 We hope that this study will provide insights into the use and practices of ORCID in the
126 Spanish scholarly ecosystem and may serve to inspire further research that helps to
127 enhance the understanding of scholars in the adoption of ORCID in their work and the
128 compromise of scientific and academic organizations in facilitating training and
129 infrastructure to its adoption.

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131 **1.1. Literature review**

132 ORCID is considered a data source that can facilitate meta-research by enhancing the
133 visibility of a wider array of scientific activities and promoting open science practices
134 (Costas et al., 2022), thus contributing to the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).
135 This potential use of ORCID has been revealed as fundamental in advancement and

136 recognition within the scientific field, highlighting their importance in documenting and
137 making these aspects visible. Moreover, ORCID is particularly renowned for its support
138 of author identifiers and its interoperability with other databases and systems (Velez-
139 Estevez et al., 2023).

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141 In examining the integration of ORCID with other databases, studies have demonstrated
142 its efficacy in elucidating the dynamics of scientific research. For example, the prevalence
143 of ORCID records in databases such as PubMed and MEDLINE is more pronounced in
144 systems where metadata is collected automatically rather than requiring manual input by
145 authors (Boudry, 2021). Additional research highlights successful integrations of ORCID
146 within other data sources. For example, CrossRef and PubMed have incorporated ORCID
147 identifiers to streamline author identification and enhance the accuracy of publication
148 records (Boudry, 2021; Haak et al., 2012). An analysis using the Dimensions database
149 found that different regions adopted and actively used ORCID IDs at different rates.
150 Portugal and Australia seemed to be ahead of the curve. This difference might be because
151 some funding agencies require ORCID IDs, and the importance of ORCID IDs also likely
152 varies depending on the specific field of research (Porter, 2022).

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154 DataCite, another metadata source, has been examined for its linkage with research
155 institutions. Findings indicate an increase in best practices such as incorporating ORCID
156 identifiers. Nevertheless, there is a need for improved connections between data and
157 associated publications (Van Wettere, 2021). Recognizing these advancements in
158 enhancing metadata's role in research, ORCID's contributions are not limited to metadata
159 improvement alone. ORCID's role extends to facilitating scientific evaluation processes,
160 mapping data sources that were previously difficult to access, and supporting equitable
161 and representative evaluation of research contributions (Haak et al., 2018).

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163 Despite these advancements in metadata improvement and scientific evaluation, the
164 adoption and perception of ORCID vary significantly across different regions and
165 institutions. In Toulouse's scientific complex, 41.8% of personnel have adopted ORCID,
166 but its use varies among disciplines such as Health and Economics, revealing a limited
167 understanding and utilization of this identifier (Heusse & Cabanac, 2022). Similarly, a
168 study of Irish faculty members at the Technological Universities and Institutes of
169 Technology in Ireland found that while more than two-thirds have an ORCID profile, it
170 is mainly used for promoting their work. Notably, there is a significant negative
171 perception towards ORCID, with concerns about its purpose, external pressure to register,
172 (from universities, journals, and funders), fears of being monitored (concerns over
173 inaccuracies in tracking academic or teaching activities), reluctance to keep profiles
174 updated, and worries over security and privacy vulnerabilities (Houghton & Foster,
175 2024).

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177 Within the university framework, a range of practices and perceptions are observed, as
178 universities are integrating ORCID identifiers into their institutional repositories and
179 researcher profile systems to improve data management and ensure consistent researcher

180 profiles (Thomas et al., 2015). While at the University of Caen in Normandy, a study by
181 Boudry and Durand-Barthez (2020) analyzed the presence of researchers across several
182 academic networking platforms, including ORCID, ResearchID, Academia.edu, and
183 ResearchGate. The findings revealed that 64.3% of researchers had profiles on both
184 ORCID and ResearchGate, with ResearchGate being the more widely used platform.
185 Despite this, the study highlighted a relatively low adoption rate of ORCID and
186 ResearchID, compounded by the absence of comprehensive publication references
187 within these profiles. This lack of detailed bibliometric information poses significant
188 challenges for accurate bibliometric evaluation and the broader aim of promoting open
189 science practices. In Portugal, the Faculty of Arts and Humanities at the University of
190 Porto showed a high ORCID adoption rate (90.4%), but the records were often
191 incomplete, impacting the disambiguation of authors. This study emphasized
192 inconsistencies in affiliation information, underscoring the need for institutional support
193 and interoperability to ensure the completeness and accuracy of profiles (Fernández-
194 Marcial et al., 2023). Similarly, at Emory University's School of Law, the challenges
195 faced in promoting the adoption of ORCID among legal researchers were identified, given
196 that their publishing and communication models are more traditional than in the sciences.
197 Continuous training and dissemination were highlighted as essential solutions for the
198 ideal adoption of this persistent identifier (Quinn, 2023).

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200 Similarly, since its introduction in Spanish institutions in 2013, initiated by the University
201 of Oviedo and backed by the FECYT, ORCID's integration has signified a pivotal shift
202 towards enhancing interoperability within research infrastructures. This move reflects a
203 strong dedication to refining research methodologies and governance of ORCID, thereby
204 bolstering its application across Spain's scientific landscape (Marín-Arraiza & Mejias,
205 2020). This evolution resonates with key principles and frameworks such as the DORA
206 principles (American Society for Cell Biology, n.d.), the Leiden Manifesto (Hicks et al.,
207 2015), CoARA (2022), the recent Spanish university law ("Ley Orgánica 2/2023, de 22
208 de marzo, del Sistema Universitario," 2023), the National Strategy for Open Science
209 2023-2027 (Ministry of Science and Innovation, 2023), and the Barcelona Declaration on
210 Open Research Information (2024).

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212 ORCID's alignment with these initiatives underscores its crucial role in reinforcing
213 standardization and academic recognition, promoting integrity, collaboration, and the
214 dissemination of knowledge within the research community (Marín-Arraiza & Mejias,
215 2020). The current Spanish scenario provides the opportunity to reflect on the use of PIDs
216 and explore optimal strategies for their implementation or integration into existing open
217 science processes (Marín-Arraiza, 2022), addressing metadata accessibility issues and
218 further consolidating the framework of an open information ecosystem (Delgado-López-
219 Cozar & Martín-Martín, 2024).

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221 In light of the broader discussions on the strategic use of PIDs, it is important to examine
222 specific studies that illustrate ORCID adoption within the Spanish research community.
223 To date, we know that in Spain, found that the ORCID identifier is included in most

224 articles published in Q1 and Q2 Spanish open access journals, with a predominant
 225 presence in Q1 journals, and that the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) is the
 226 leading Spanish scientific publisher that has adopted it in its editorial management,
 227 suggesting that the ORCID identifier could become a criterion for editorial quality
 228 (Martínez Méndez & López Carreño, 2019). Bordons et al. (2024) analyzed ORCID
 229 adoption in Spanish scientific articles and among ERC grant recipients in Spain. They
 230 found that almost 90% of articles list at least one ORCID ID, but only 14% include
 231 ORCID IDs for all authors. All ERC grantees had ORCID IDs, with 50% updating their
 232 profiles monthly. Differences by gender, discipline, and funding scheme were also
 233 examined, insisting that publisher and journal policies are essential to drive ORCID
 234 adoption.

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236 **2. METHODOLOGY**

237 **2.1. Dataset generation**

238 We utilized ORCID and OpenAlex as open data sources for our analysis. From ORCID's
 239 public annual snapshot of September 2023, we collected data on over 17 million profiles.
 240 These profiles provided a rich set of metadata, including identification details,
 241 employment affiliations, educational background, publication lists, and peer review
 242 contributions, as summarized in Table 1. It also provides information about metadata
 243 update logs. Additionally, we accessed data from OpenAlex, updated to April 2024,
 244 through the InSySPo cluster to enrich our analysis by retrieving additional ORCID
 245 profiles and uniquely identifying researchers and their main research areas.

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247 **Table 1.** ORCID record metadata analyzed

Section	Field	Description
Profile identification data	Name	Full name
	Other names	Name variants
	Biography	Brief professional career description
	Email(s)	Email address(es)
	Websites and social media links	Links to websites and social media profiles
	Other IDs	Researcher identifiers like ISNI, Scopus Author ID, ResearcherID
	Keywords	Words describing research activity
	Countries	Country of professional activity
Activities	Employment	Information about professional affiliations with organizations
	Education and qualifications	Details on educational institutions and degrees or professional qualifications
	Professional activities	Details about affiliations with various organizations, societies, or associations, and roles in supporting these entities
	Funding	Details on grants, awards, and other types of research support funding
	Works	Publications, books, conferences, and other academic contributions
Additional feature	Peer review	Allows users to link and display their contributions as reviewers on their ORCID profile, documenting their participation in peer review processes

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249 To construct the sample, we conducted three searches to collect our dataset. First, from
 250 the ORCID public snapshot of September 2023, we collected records listing a Spanish
 251 affiliation in the 'Employment' field. Second, we included records from the same ORCID
 252 snapshot where the 'Country' field was listed as Spain. Third, we used the OpenAlex
 253 public snapshot, updated as of April 2024 and accessed through the InSySPo cluster, to
 254 identify additional ORCID records of Spanish researchers that were not retrievable by the
 255 previous methods. We retrieved records of Spanish authors whose last known affiliation
 256 is a Spanish institution and filtered authors having an ORCID ID (15.88%). This last filter
 257 allowed us to identify 19% of records (44,055) that have no affiliation or country
 258 associated with them, making it impossible to locate using ORCID alone. These three
 259 searches were combined to avoid duplication, resulting in a dataset of 226,511 records.
 260 Figure 1 illustrates the steps followed for retrieving the Spanish ORCID records.

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Figure 1. Summary of Spanish ORCID records retrieval process

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265 **2.2. Researchers and main research area identification**

266 To determine the use of ORCID in Spain, and to exclude non-researcher profiles such as
 267 librarians, technical staff, etc., we carried out a procedure to identify researchers as
 268 comprehensively as possible among all individuals in our dataset. It should be noted that
 269 this process does not attempt to identify precisely the different academic positions or to
 270 limit ourselves to those within the university or research centre, but rather to identify all
 271 those who have carried out research activities, and to avoid including profiles that are
 272 significantly different. First, we used the last self-declared role in their ORCID record in
 273 the Employment field. In total, 139,335 (61.5%) of the ORCID profiles have a role listed.
 274 However, it lacks standardization, with 43,086 unique roles. Manually, this field was
 275 cleaned using basic text mining techniques, eliminating special characters, transforming
 276 text strings to lowercase, and correcting errors such as double spaces. However, this
 277 reduced the number of roles to 38,250. Therefore, the 2,794 most common roles, which
 278 appear in 70% of the ORCID records that include this field, were manually reviewed to

279 identify which were academic roles and which were not. Subsequently, matches were
280 sought for terms marked as researcher profiles among the remaining 30% of roles. In
281 total, 23,678 roles were identified as academic, thus marking 77% of ORCID users in this
282 field as researchers, representing 47% of the general dataset. To this process, we have
283 added the tagging as a researcher of all ORCID records present in OpenAlex, as well as
284 all ORCID records with a Web of Science or Scopus identifier or more than 4 journal
285 publications. It should be noted that there may be discrepancies between the different
286 processes, but the approach is to be as inclusive as possible and to have the broadest
287 possible representation of researchers. In total, for the complete dataset, 190,455 (80%)
288 were marked as researchers, and these are the records to be used in this study.

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290 On the other hand, for the identification of the main research area of each ORCID record,
291 data from both ORCID and OpenAlex were utilized. First, we retrieved all DOIs (Digital
292 Object Identifiers) of the publications listed in each ORCID profile. Next, using these
293 DOIs, we located all corresponding publications indexed in the OpenAlex database.
294 Additionally, for all authors indexed in OpenAlex with an ORCID identifier, we retrieved
295 all their publications from OpenAlex. Secondly, for all ORCID records present in
296 OpenAlex, all their publications were retrieved. After that, using the OpenAlex
297 classification system of citation topics developed by CWTS, a count of the domains
298 associated with each publication was carried out. This is the highest hierarchical level of
299 the topic classification and consists of the 4 main areas (Life Sciences, Social Sciences,
300 Physical Sciences, and Health Sciences). In this way, each ORCID record was associated
301 with a domain in which it had the most publications, with the possibility of a tie in some
302 cases.

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304 **2.3. Methods**

305 For the data analysis, various statistical methods were applied using R. Initially,
306 descriptive statistics were employed to explore the characteristics, activity, and age of
307 ORCID records for Spanish researchers, as well as the metadata they complete. This
308 initial analysis provided an overview of the dataset, highlighting key trends and patterns
309 in the information provided by researchers. To gain a more detailed understanding, we
310 expanded this study by analyzing the intersections of fields within these records, utilizing
311 UpSet plots. These plots allowed us to visualize the combinations of metadata fields that
312 are most frequently filled, offering insights into how researchers populate their profiles.
313 All data and scripts used for this analysis are available on Zenodo
314 ([10.5281/zenodo.12019457](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12019457)) and GitHub
315 (https://github.com/Wences91/spanish_orcids/tree/main).

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317 **3. RESULTS**

318 **3.1. Activity of Spanish researchers in ORCID**

319 There are 190,455 Spanish researchers registered in ORCID, with 139,004 (73%) being
320 active accounts, indicating recent activity within the last year (September 2022 to
321 September 2023). The data shows a significant increase in profile creation starting in
322 2012, with a marked peak between 2014 and 2017 (Figure 2a). This period saw the highest

323 number of registrations, a total of 94,152 new records (49%). The adoption of ORCID
 324 profiles in Spain has shown a significant upward trend over recent years. This surge can
 325 be attributed to several factors, primarily the increasing mandates from academic
 326 institutions and scholarly journals. Universities and research organizations in Spain have
 327 progressively required their faculty and researchers to register for ORCID iDs to ensure
 328 accurate attribution of their work and to streamline administrative processes.
 329 Additionally, many academic journals now mandate ORCID iDs for authors as part of the
 330 submission process, aiming to enhance the integrity and traceability of scholarly
 331 publications. These institutional and editorial requirements have collectively driven a
 332 substantial increase in ORCID registrations, resulting in a notable peak in the number of
 333 profiles created. Following this peak, there is a noticeable decline in new ORCID profile
 334 creations, continuing through 2023. However, it is important to note that the ORCID data
 335 only covers up to September 2023. This trend suggests a stabilization in the adoption of
 336 ORCID among Spanish researchers, possibly indicating that most eligible researchers
 337 have already registered. The decrease in new registrations could also reflect a maturation
 338 of the ORCID system within Spain. Initially, the growth was rapid due to increased
 339 awareness and the implementation of mandatory policies, whereas the current growth rate
 340 is more aligned with the natural influx of new researchers entering the system. Additional
 341 factors contributing to the decline may include the saturation of the target population,
 342 reduced promotional efforts, administrative challenges, a perceived lack of utility by
 343 some researchers, and the use of alternative identification systems (ORCID, 2024b).

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Figure 2. Distribution of Spanish ORCID records by a) creation date, b) years since last update, c) and years since last update per creation date

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350 The distribution of Spanish ORCID profiles based on the years since their last update
351 reveals that the majority have been updated within the past year (58%), highlighting a
352 high level of recent activity and engagement (Figure 2b). The frequency of profile updates
353 declines sharply after one year, with a significant drop in profiles not updated for more
354 than one year (16%). The analysis of update frequency, categorized by the year of profile
355 creation, shows that the median time since the last update remains around one year across
356 all creation years (Figure 2c). This regular updating behavior reflects an active academic
357 community that maintains their profiles to keep their information current despite the
358 ORCID record age. While a core group of researchers remains highly active, there are
359 segments of the research community that update less frequently, which could reflect
360 diverse career stages and varying degrees of ongoing research activity.

361 The observed high frequency of recent updates may also be influenced by institutional
362 infrastructures that automatically update researchers' profiles. Many universities and
363 research institutions integrate ORCID with their internal systems, ensuring that profiles
364 are kept up to date with minimal effort from individual researchers. This automation
365 supports continuous and consistent profile management, contributing to the overall
366 activity levels observed.

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368 However, these data primarily indicate that most profiles show a certain degree of
369 activity, regardless of the age of the registration. They do not, however, clearly reflect the
370 extent to which these updates maintain the profiles' completeness and accuracy. In the
371 following section, the level of completeness of the profiles will be examined in more
372 detail to better understand the adoption and usage of this platform by Spanish researchers.

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374 **3.2. Metadata analysis**

375 The metadata analysis of Spanish ORCID records (Figure 3a) reveals notable disparities
376 in the completeness of various sections. Overall, 83% of the records include information
377 in the 'Works' section and 73% in the 'Employment' section. However, other sections,
378 such as 'Keywords' (27%), 'Other names' (20%), and 'Peer review' (19%), are less
379 frequently completed. Of the 13 fields studied, only 4 reflect values above 50%. This
380 disparity can stem from multiple factors such as a lack of activity in specific areas (e.g.,
381 professional activities or funding grants) or insufficient information to provide in certain
382 fields (e.g., alternative names). Privacy concerns (e.g., email or address) or lack of
383 connections to other platforms (e.g., peer review or other IDs) can also contribute to these
384 differences. In cases such as 'Keywords', the lower levels of information could be due to
385 a lack of interest or lack of knowledge on the part of the researchers themselves.

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387 In contrast, the analysis of active and non-active Spanish ORCID records provides deeper
388 insights into these information presence trends. Active records show a significantly higher
389 presence of information in the main sections, specifically 90% for 'Works' and 73% for
390 'Employment'. Active profiles also show moderate levels of information in 'Education
391 and Qualifications' (54%) and 'Other IDs' (58%). However, there is less information
392 included in sections such as 'Keywords' (29%) and 'Peer review' (25%). On the other

393 hand, non-active records have noticeably lower levels of information across most
 394 sections. For instance, only 65% of non-active profiles have data included in the ‘Works’
 395 section, and 49% have information in the ‘Employment’ section. The low levels of
 396 information for sections such as ‘Email’ (7%) and ‘Professional Activities’ (6%) in non-
 397 active profiles highlight the broader issue of outdated or minimally maintained records.
 398 This gap between active and non-active profiles suggests that many researchers may
 399 create ORCID accounts primarily for initial use and then neglect to update them regularly,
 400 leading to incomplete and less useful records.

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Figure 3. Availability of metadata in Spanish ORCID researcher records: a) all records;
 b) active records; c) non-active records

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Beyond the percentage of records that include a specific field, it is essential to consider how these fields appear together. Among all possible combinations, the 20 most frequent cover 69,251 records (36%), with a total of 8,178 possible combinations. The most common case is the record that only includes ‘Works’, with 11,423 records (6%), followed by those that include ‘Works’, ‘Employment’, and ‘Education and Qualifications’ (4%) (Figure 4a). This is expected, given that 6 of the 13 analyzed fields appear in only 20% or fewer records. When this analysis excludes these less-used fields, the most frequent case is the one that includes ‘Works’, ‘Employment’, ‘Education and Qualifications’, and ‘Other IDs’ (7%) (Figure 4b). When selecting only fields present in at least 50% of the records (Figure 4c), the most frequent case again involves all these fields (27%). This underscores the complexity of accounting for fields and profiles, ultimately reflecting a broad diversity of profiles. Despite this, there does appear to be a dominant pattern, particularly among records that include all four fields.

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Figure 4. Top 20 metadata intersections of Spanish ORCID records considering: a) all ORCID fields, b) only ORCID fields with a prevalence of more than 20%, and c) only ORCID fields with a prevalence of more than 50%

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3.3. Differences across research domains

Researchers were classified into four major areas of knowledge or domains according to OpenAlex (Table 2): Life Sciences, Social Sciences, Physical Sciences, and Health Sciences. The majority of ORCID records fall under Physical Sciences (37.9%), followed by Social Sciences (26.3%), Health Sciences (24.6%), and Life Sciences (18%). Notably, over 80% of the records in each domain are active, indicating strong engagement from researchers regardless of the domain. The average number of journal publications is highest in the Physical Sciences (31.4) and Health Sciences (28.3). There is a slight bias because classifying ORCID profiles by domain requires at least one publication, but even with this bias, the average number of journal publications remains high at 25.9. Additionally, there are epistemic differences across the sciences, with Social Sciences having the lowest average number of publications (15.1), which, although lower, is still relatively high. In the end, what this elevated average indicates is that researchers who provide publication data tend to have a higher volume of publications.

445 **Table 2.** Distribution of Spanish ORCID records across research domains and average
 446 publications

	Life Sciences	Social Sciences	Physical Sciences	Health Sciences	Total
<i>ORCID records</i>	26,864 (18%)	39,277 (26.3%)	56,513 (37.9%)	36,638 (24.6%)	149,182 (100%)
<i>Active records</i>	21,629 (80.5%)	31,356 (79.8%)	45,644 (80.8%)	30,073 (82.1%)	122,836 (82.3%)
<i>Avg. Works</i>	30,1 ±47.9	25.6 ±42.4	40.6 ±86	30.9 ±68.3	32.9 ±67.5
<i>Avg. Journal publications</i>	27 ±44	15.1 ±24	31.4 ±75.1	28.3 ±59.8	25.9 ±57.7

447 **Note:** ‘Works’ refers to the total elements whereas ‘Journal publications’ are the works
 448 published in journals.
 449

450 There are differences and commonalities in how Spanish researchers across different
 451 domains populate their ORCID profiles (Figure 5). Employment information is
 452 prominently featured across all fields, with notable percentages such as 69% in Health
 453 Sciences and 78% in Social Sciences. Similarly, fields like 'Education and qualifications'
 454 and 'Other IDs' also show high percentages, especially in domains like Life Sciences and
 455 Physical Sciences, reflecting an emphasis or predominance of multiple academic
 456 identifiers. In contrast, less emphasis is placed on fields such as 'Keywords' and 'Peer
 457 review', with 'Keywords' appearing most frequently in Social Sciences at 38% and 'Peer
 458 review' in Physical Sciences at 27%. While some metadata fields are universally
 459 prioritized, others are more domain-specific. In this sense, Social Sciences consistently
 460 show higher percentages across multiple fields, indicating a more comprehensive
 461 approach to metadata entry compared to other domains.

462 **Figure 5.** Availability of metadata in Spanish ORCID researcher records across research
 463 domains
 464

465

466

467 **4. DISCUSSION**

468 Our study reveals a strong representation of Spanish researchers in ORCID, especially
469 among those actively engaged in research, providing a clear response to the inquiry
470 regarding their ORCID involvement (Porter, 2022). It is evident from the metadata
471 analysis that 'Employment' and 'Publications' are the sections most frequently populated
472 by Spanish researchers in their ORCID profiles, emphasizing the importance placed on
473 career affiliation and scholarly outputs (Youtie et al., 2017). However, not all metadata
474 sections in an ORCID record are completed exhaustively, leading to profiles that are
475 partially filled (Fernández-Marcial et al., 2023; Heusse & Cabanac, 2022), which may
476 inadvertently result in the undervaluation of other academic contributions and activities.

477

478 The completeness of metadata sections in ORCID records varies, and the presence of
479 partially filled profiles could pose challenges to their application in science of science
480 research (Thompson et al., 2022). Incomplete records may skew the data and lead to
481 inaccuracies in the analysis, affecting the validity of studies that rely on this information.
482 This issue of data integrity becomes critical when considering ORCID as an open
483 metadata source for science of science research (Costas et al., 2022).

484

485 The principle of interoperability, when applied to the automatic updating of ORCID
486 profiles by various stakeholders within the research ecosystem, could markedly
487 ameliorate the issue of incomplete metadata. By fostering an interoperable framework
488 where research institutions, publishers, funding bodies, and ORCID seamlessly exchange
489 data, we can ensure that a researcher's profile is consistently updated with the latest
490 publications, grants, and affiliations. This level of integration would significantly
491 improve the accuracy and completeness of ORCID records, enhancing its reliability as a
492 resource for science studies (Baglioni et al., 2021). Interoperability facilitates not only
493 the ease of data sharing across different platforms but also minimizes the manual effort
494 required from researchers to maintain their profiles. Consequently, ORCID emerges as a
495 more reliable, comprehensive open resource for documenting academic achievements,
496 strengthening the foundation for in-depth analysis in science of science research.

497

498 Despite the benefits of name disambiguation (Sixto-Costoya et al., 2021), ORCID's
499 detailed records could play a pivotal role in addressing and preventing authorship fraud.
500 While our study has underlined the robust adoption of ORCID identifiers among Spanish
501 researchers, it also ventures into the realm of academic integrity, demonstrating how the
502 platform's capacity for detailed record-keeping aids in the combat against fraudulent
503 practices (Baglioni et al., 2021; Teixeira da Silva, 2023).

504

505 By linking ORCID profiles of authors with Spanish affiliations, both active and inactive,
506 to the OpenAlex database, our investigation gains a nuanced understanding of
507 engagement levels with the ORCID system. This comprehensive approach reveals a
508 landscape of ORCID engagement among Spanish researchers that is both committed and
509 variable. Coupled with our calculations of the average profile update frequency, this

510 enriched data set provides a solid foundation for identifying discrepancies that may
511 indicate academic misconduct (Khezr & Mohan, 2022; Teixeira da Silva, 2020). Our
512 analysis suggests that the maintenance patterns of ORCID profiles, particularly the
513 frequency of updates, can serve as indicators for potential 'paper mills' or phantom
514 accounts (Teixeira da Silva, 2021a). Anomalies such as unusually high rates of profile
515 updates or irregular co-authorship patterns, further highlighted by their OpenAlex
516 associations, might signal fraudulent activities within the academic community.

517

518 Leveraging ORCID's comprehensive data, our study not only showcases the utility of
519 ORCID within Spain but also emphasizes its potential to safeguard the research
520 community from integrity threats. This presents an opportunity to develop a procedure for the
521 Spanish institutional research system, guiding decision-makers, integrity research offices, and
522 institutional ethical committees on best practices in scholarly communications and research. This
523 approach aligns with methodologies to those proposed by Porter and McIntosh (2024),
524 —enhanced by OpenAlex data—to improve transparency and traceability in scholarly
525 contributions, thus strengthening the credibility of academic work.

526

527 Therefore, exploring the ramifications of ORCID's metadata richness is crucial not only
528 in reflecting the active engagement of Spanish researchers but also as a potential asset in
529 research ethics and integrity studies, as well as in the broader context of academic data
530 ecosystems (Wouters et al., 2019).

531

532 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

533 This study provides a detailed overview of the adoption and use of ORCID by researchers
534 in Spain. The results highlight a strong presence of active Spanish researcher profiles on
535 ORCID, confirming the significance of this tool for managing academic identity and
536 scientific visibility.

537

538 The uptake of ORCID among the Spanish academic community is robust, particularly
539 among those actively engaged in research. The 'Employment' and 'Publications' sections
540 are the most completed, highlighting the importance of professional affiliation and
541 research outputs. Despite the high rate of active profiles, there is variability in the
542 completeness of the metadata sections. This suggests that while ORCID is a valuable tool,
543 its potential is not being fully realized due to partially completed and private profiles
544 (Wang et al., 2024). Besides, as ORCID is recognized as potentially playing a crucial role
545 in preventing authorship fraud (Teixeira da Silva, 2023), the interoperability with other
546 databases and automatic updating of profiles by other entities in the research ecosystem
547 (such as institutions, publishers, and funders) could significantly improve the
548 completeness of metadata, thereby increasing the reliability of ORCID to carried out this
549 type of studies (Teixeira da Silva, 2022; Bordons et al., 2024).

550

551 For future research, we plan to investigate the potential of ORCID as a tool for tracking
552 researcher mobility and understanding academic trajectories. By analyzing ORCID
553 records that include Spanish affiliations, we aim to conduct detailed mobility studies that

554 trace career progressions and geographic movements over time. This investigation will
555 utilize the sequential order of affiliations within ORCID profiles, providing insights into
556 the academic pathways and international flow of knowledge. Such research could
557 illuminate patterns of researcher mobility, identify factors influencing academic career
558 choices, and contribute to strategic planning in research policy and workforce
559 development.

560

561 Several limitations should be considered in this research. The results of this research
562 depend on the sources and the query used for data collection and comparison. On the one
563 hand, although OpenAlex may be the most comprehensive database due to its open access
564 (Visser et al., 2021), its integration with other data sources, and its support for open
565 science and FAIR principles, it is possible that not all Spanish researchers are included.
566 On the other hand, our sample could be affected by the OpenAlex author disambiguation,
567 since cases of inconsistency have been detected (Culbert et al., 2024).

568

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570 For further insights into the InSySPo infrastructure and associated projects, access the
571 GitHub repositories at <https://github.com/insyspo> and <https://github.com/alyssonmazoni>.

572

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